

IPPT_TWINN - Reinforcing the scientific excellence and innovation capacity
in polymer processing technologies
of the Faculty of Polymer Technology

**WP1 – ADVANCED HYBRID PROCESSING
TECHNOLOGIES FOR FUTURE DEMANDS
D1.2 CHARACTERISED PROPERTIES
OF CAN AND COMPOSITES**

PROJECT: 101079051 — IPPT_TWINN — HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-03

VERSION 1.0

Date of delivery: 27.4.2024

Author(s): Rebeka Lorber, Tajda Glamočak, Tadej Slatinek, Matic Petrič, Klementina
Pušnik Črešnar, Irena Pulko, Janez Slapnik, Blaž Nardin

Contact details

Project coordinator: Blaž Nardin, FTPO, blaz.nardin@ftpo.eu, +386 31 301 243

Exploitation manager: Maja Mešl, maja.mesl@ftpo.eu, +386 51 315 970

Address: Faculty of Polymer Technology (FTPO), Ozare 19, 2380 Slovenj Gradec, Slovenia

Project details

Project Number	101079051
Project Acronym	IPPT_TWINN
Project Name	Reinforcing the scientific excellence and innovation capacity in polymer processing technologies of the Faculty of Polymer Technology
Starting date	1 st January 2023
Duration in months	36
Call (part) identifier	HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-03
Action	Twinning - Institutional networking

Document details

Work Package	WP1 - Advanced hybrid processing technologies for future demands
Task	1.2
Deliverable number	D1.2
Version	V1
File name	D1.2_Characterized properties of CAN and composites_V1
Type of deliverable	Report
Dissemination Level	Public
Work package leader	FTPO
Task leader	FTPO
Author	Rebeka Lorber, Tajda Glamočak, Tadej Slatinek, Matic Petrič, Klementina Pušnik Črešnar, Irena Pulko, Janez Slapnik, Blaž Nardin
Due date	30.4.2024
Submission Date	28.4.2024

Version management

Revision history and quality check			
Version	Name	Date	Comment
V1	D1.2_Characterized properties of CAN and composites_V1	27.4.2024	

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of Contents

Executive summary	7
Introduction	8
Methods used	10
Experimental results	20
Reactive mixing	20
Dissociative CAN trials.....	31
Upscaling	33
Conclusions	50
Deviations from the GA.....	51
References.....	52

List of Figures

Figure 1: Covalent adaptable networks as a bridge between thermosets and thermoplastics ³	8
Figure 2: Brabender Plasti-Corder Lab-Station EC (Mixer 50 EHT).....	11
Figure 3: Reaction setup (left) and product (right)	12
Figure 4: Hydraulic pressing of the sample	12
Figure 5: Twin screw extruder.....	17
Figure 6: Moment (blue) and temperature (red) versus time for mixing of PP-MAH with optimal parameters	20
Figure 7: Multiple samples increase after an initial spike in the moment (blue curve) was noticed, indicating successful crosslinking.....	21
Figure 8: NMR spectra of PO 1020.....	22
Figure 9: FT-IR spectra of reference mixed PO1020 (005) and references with crosslinkers in PO1020 only (006 – DGEBA, 013 – DDO, 019 – BDO, 064 – PETMP and 070 – diPETMP)	23
Figure 10: ATR-FTIR spectra of reference mixed PO1020 (005) and reference samples with catalysts only (007 – ZnAc, 025 – TBD, and 048 – TPP)	23
Figure 11: ATR-FTIR spectra of reference mixed PO1020 (005) and samples with ZnAc as catalyst and various crosslinkers (009 – DGEBA, 015 – DDO, 021 – BDO, 077 – PETMP and 082 – diPETMP).....	24
Figure 12: ATR-FTIR spectra of reference mixed PO1020 (005) and samples with TBD as catalyst and various crosslinkers (027 – DGEBA, 032 – DDO, 037 – BDO, 066 – PETMP and 072 – diPETMP).....	25
Figure 13: ATR-FTIR spectra of reference mixed PO1020 (005) and samples with TPP as catalyst and various crosslinkers (050 – DGEBA, 055 – DDO, 060 – BDO, 087 – PETMP and 092 – diPETMP).....	25
Figure 14: ATR-FTIR spectra of reference mixed PO1020 (005) and representative samples of systems without catalyst (042 – with 2,2-DTA and 045 – with 4,4-DTA)	26
Figure 15: Reference DSC curves as an example of evaluation.....	27
Figure 16: DSC thermographs of sample 009	27
Figure 17: Reference TGA curves as an example of evaluation	29
Figure 18: Temperatures of degradation and onset temperatures of degradation of reference and representative samples	29
Figure 19: Representative dynamic modulus versus temperature curve	30
Figure 20: Dynamic Modulus at 30 °C and 130 °C	30
Figure 21: Gel content determination results for PP-MAH based mixtures	31
Figure 22: Reference solid-state NMR spectra of PP-MAH powder crosslinked with BMI in ratio 1:2 (BMI:MA groups).....	32
Figure 23: ATR-FTIR spectra of reference, intermediates, and materials with Diels-Alder mechanism	32
Figure 24: NMR spectra of ABS-MAH (Graftabond ABS-MAH 00320)	33
Figure 25: NMR spectra of PP-MAH (Graftabond APP-MAH 00530 C)	34
Figure 26: ATR-FTIR spectra of PP based specimens as follows PP (822_2024_0005_01_PP), PP-MAH (822_2024_0005_02_PP-g-MA), PP-V1 (822_2024_0005_03_PP V), PP-V2 (822_2024_0005_10_PP V2) and PP-V3 (822_2024_0005_11_PP V3).....	35
Figure 27: ATR-FTIR spectra of ABS based specimens as follows ABS (822_2024_0005_04_ABS), ABS-MAH (822_2024_0005_05_ABS-g-MA), ABS-V1 (822_2024_0005_06_ABS V), ABS-V2 (822_2024_0005_08_ABS V2) and ABS-V3 (822_2024_0005_ABS V3)	35
Figure 28: Melt flow index of initially upscaled mixtures	36
Figure 29: MFI of second batch of upscaled mixtures	37
Figure 30: Gel content of ABS-V1.....	37
Figure 31: ABS-V3 in metallic net in acetone	38
Figure 32: Filtering of ABS based samples dissolved in acetone by filter paper.....	38
Figure 33: Gel content of ABS based vitrimers determined via filtration	39

Figure 34: Dissolved injection molded ABS-V3 specimen in two parallels	39
Figure 35: Stress-strain curves of PP (left) and ABS (right) based vitrimers	40
Figure 36: Determination of optimal bonding parameters.....	40
Figure 37: Adhesion testing before (left) and after (right).....	41
Figure 38: Adhesion testing - parameter determination results	41
Figure 39: Adhesion of PP-MAH welded with ABS-MAH compared to PP-V3 welded with ABS-V3.....	42
Figure 40: FTIR spectra of ABS-V3 component ratio design of experiment.....	43
Figure 41: Dynamic modulus (logarithmic) versus temperature plots for ABS-V3 design of experiments	44
Figure 42: Stress-strain representative curves for ABS-V3 design of experiments.....	45
Figure 43: FTIR spectra of PP-V3 based composites	45
Figure 44: Melt flow index of composites.....	46
Figure 45: TGA thermographs of composites	47
Figure 46: Representative stress-strain curves of composites.....	47
Figure 47: PP-V3-C1% welded with ABS-V3 bonding force versus strain.....	48
Figure 48: Bonding and debonding tests of PP-V3C1% welded with ABS-V3.....	49

List of tables

Table 1: PP-MAH based CANs prepared via mixing and dissolving.....	13
Table 2: Materials prepared via reactive extrusion.....	16
Table 3: Design of experiments for ABS-V3.....	16
Table 4: Composite formulations	16
Table 5: Injection molding parameters	17
Table 6: Equipment overview	19
Table 7: DSC results of reference samples and representative sample for each combination.....	28
Table 8: Melt flow index results	43
Table 9: Glass transitions and corresponding specific heats determined using DSC.....	43
Table 10: Gathered results of thermogravimetric analysis	44
Table 11: DSC results of composites	46

Executive summary

Plastic consumption is rising sharply, leading to increased waste and CO₂ emissions. To combat this, the IPPT_TWINN project aims to produce more durable products and use cleaner processing methods. By collaborating with partners across Europe, including workshops and research, the project will enhance polymer processing knowledge. This effort will result in more publications, making FTPO a desirable partner for institutions and industries. Additionally, the project prioritizes training young researchers in proposal preparation and partnership building.

The main objective of work package 1 (WP1), titled Advanced hybrid processing technologies for future demands, is to create a hybrid technology for producing high-performance multicomponent structures with a recyclable thermoplastic matrix. This innovative approach combines the strengths of thermoplastic resin transfer molding (T-RTM) and/or injection molding with additive manufacturing in a single production process. By integrating these techniques, the project seeks to enhance efficiency and sustainability in multipart component manufacturing. Given WP consists of 5 tasks, namely Study of the interfacial bonding strength (T1.1), Synthesis of covalent adaptable networks (CANs) using reactive extrusion and compounding (T1.2), Study of improvement of interfacial bonding strength between different polymers (T1.3), Use of CAN in hybrid technologies (T1.4) and Development of demonstrators (T1.5).

The main goal of T1.2 was to develop new materials containing covalent adaptable networks via reactive extrusion or compounding employing a laboratory twin-screw extruder. Additionally, to covalent adaptable bonds induction, the modification of CANs with functional fillers, to enable spatially selective heating to facilitate thermal triggering of covalent bond transitions, was planned. For this purpose, carbon nanotubes and graphite were used. The properties in new materials were planned to be evaluated using Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) and Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) for chemical insights, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) for thermal properties and mechanical evaluations dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) and tensile testing were employed. The hypothesis was that substantial changes in mechanical properties would be noticed, however, in crystalline polymers, this might not be always positive, due to the reduction of crystallinity and competitiveness of crosslinking reactions with chain-scission reactions.

The material development that could serve as a reversible glue between two parts, thus enabling triggered bonding and debonding and therefore easy recycling of multicomponent (composite) parts since recycling the products made with a combination of various polymers is usually complicated and does not give good results. Thus, many aspects would benefit including environment, sustainability, circularity, etc., from solutions that would be straightforward, uncomplicated, and would give good results. With this in mind, covalent adaptable network (CAN) systems act as reversible glue in the welding of incompatible materials and enable trigger debonding as well. The goal of T1.2 of WP1 was to yield materials with such functionality. The results gathered from the characterization of developed CANs and CAN composites are covered in the present document.

Introduction

The field of polymer materials has witnessed remarkable advancements in recent years since the discovery of covalent adaptable networks in 2011 by Leibler et al.¹, driven by the pursuit of novel materials with exceptional properties and versatility. Among these materials, CANs have emerged as an intriguing class of polymers that possess unique characteristics, including the ability to undergo dynamic, reversible bond exchanges.² This distinctive feature enables CANs to exhibit remarkable structural reconfigurability, enhanced mechanical properties, (triggerable) weldability with non-compatible counterparts of the same CAN chemistry, and the potential for self-healing besides representing materials that overcome drawbacks of two major groups of polymers – thermosets, and thermoplastics, by many authors figuratively presented as a bridge between them, such is presented in Figure 1³⁻⁵. What sets them apart is their remarkable ability to dynamically respond to specific triggers like heat, catalysts, light, or changes in pH. When exposed to these stimuli, CANs undergo reversible transformations, resulting in the thermoplastic nature of the material, and in the absence of stimuli, their behavior is usually thermoset-like. Since, even in the absence of these triggers, CANs maintain a cross-linked structure, resulting in thermoset-like properties. This means they possess increased strength and durability, reminiscent of conventional materials due to additional crosslinking.⁶

Figure 1: Covalent adaptable networks as a bridge between thermosets and thermoplastics ³

Many different chemical mechanisms provide associative bond exchange such as transesterification, transamination of vinyllogous acyls, and transalkylation. Moreover, there are many more, resulting in materials with vitrimer-like properties, such as silyl ether exchange, olefin metathesis, imine exchange, and disulfide exchange chemistry.^{3,7} Noted exchange mechanism be induced in many different polymer matrixes increasing the tailor-ability of the CANs and their properties even further.⁸

Understanding these mechanisms is crucial for tailoring the properties of CANs to meet specific application requirements. Their ability to adapt and adjust to their surroundings opens endless possibilities for their application in various industries and fields. From advanced materials to responsive technologies, CANs hold immense promise for innovation and advancement. As a result, CANs hold great promise for a wide range of applications across industries such as aerospace, automotive, electronics, and biomedical engineering.^{6,9}

In consideration of the studied literature, a plan for the development of CANs was constructed, that included the evaluation of multiple mechanisms of CANs, to yield the most appropriate material for further development, that include weldability and processability via 3D printing.

Methods used

Diving into a new field for our researchers, the first extensive literature research was carried out, which resulted in the plan for the synthesis of CANs. For the modification to prepare CANs, it was decided to use commercially available grafted polymers and modify them with suitable crosslinkers and/or catalysts. Initially, it was decided to test various chemical mechanisms of CANs on a smaller scale than the reactive compounding of materials using a kneader, as the price and consumption of such materials using an existing laboratory twin-screw extruder with a theoretical throughput of 25 kg per hour is too high compared to 30 g per batch on the kneader. The chosen polymer matrix was maleic anhydride grafted polypropylene (PP-MAH) and for initial experiments, Exxelor PO 1020 was used. The experiments were set up as follows:

- a) Modification of PP-MAH by mixing on a kneader using various catalysts and crosslinkers to obtain CANs with bond exchange via an associative mechanism, shown in Table 1, where each possible combination of catalyst and crosslinker was tested.
- b) Modification of PP-MAH by dissolving it in a solvent (xylene, as the originally intended tetrahydrofuran (THF) did not dissolve PP-MAH) to obtain CANs with bond exchange via a dissociative mechanism (namely Diels-Alder reaction mechanism).
- c) Upscaling of the most promising materials to the process of reactive compounding and other polymer matrices (ABS-MAH).

The modification of PP-MAH by mixing on a kneader was carried out on the Brabender Plasti-Corder Lab-Station EC (Mixer 50 EHT in 350 E; Figure 2) at 165 °C and 60 rpm-1 for 20 min. PP-MAH (Exxelor PO 1020) with various crosslinkers and catalysts was used as the base. Two catalyst-free systems were also tested, using 2,2-dithioniline and 4,4-dithioaniline as crosslinking agents, which act without a catalyst and induce crosslinking in which the compounds are exchanged by disulphide metathesis. Other crosslinking agents tested were diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA), 1,4-butanediol (BDO) and 1,10-decanediol (DDO), which induce crosslinking via the transesterification crosslinking mechanism. Additionally, pentaerythritol tetrakis(3-mercaptopropionate) (PETMP) and dipentaerythritol hexakis(3-mercaptopropionate) (diPETMP), which induce the thio-thiol ester exchange mechanism were used. One of the following three catalysts was used for each crosslinker: Zinc acetate (ZnAc), triazabicyclodecene (TBD) or triphenylphosphate (TPP). Each combination of crosslinker and catalyst was prepared in 5 different ratios as follows:

1. 0.5 (no. of crosslinker molecules to no. of MA groups); 0.1 (no. catalyst molecules to no. crosslinker molecules),
2. 1 (no. of crosslinker molecules to no. of MA groups); 0.1 (no. catalyst molecules to no. crosslinker molecules),
3. 2 (no. of crosslinker molecules to no. of MA groups); 0.1 (no. catalyst molecules to no. crosslinker molecules),
4. 1 (no. of crosslinker molecules to no. of MA groups); 0.2 (no. catalyst molecules to no. crosslinker molecules), and
5. 1 (no. of crosslinker molecules to no. of MA groups); 0.05 (no. catalyst molecules to no. crosslinker molecules).

Figure 2: Brabender Plasti-Corder Lab-Station EC (Mixer 50 EHT)

The modification of PP-MAH by dissolution in a solvent was performed to induce the dissociative covalent adaptable networks. The first reaction solvent tested was tetrahydrofuran (THF), but it did not dissolve PP-g-MA sufficiently, so it was necessary to switch from THF to xylenes. The dissolving of polyethylene grafted with maleic anhydride (PE-g-MA) in xylene was also tried, but the dissolution of the desired granulate was not good enough. PP-g-MA was dissolved in xylene (at 130 °C), stirred for 1 h with 3- times the molar equivalent of furfurylamine (FFA) to form maleic anhydride groups, stirred again for 1 h at 130 °C, then precipitated in distilled water and dried to constant mass. Next, the furan-substituted PP-g-MA batches (PP-g-furan) were dissolved in 200 ml of xylene at 130 °C, with one of the following ratios (BMI to MA group) of bismaleimide (BMI) added (0.5 equiv; 1 equiv or 2 equiv), and stirred for 1 h. Most of the solvent was evaporated overnight in a fume hood and the sample was dried the next day at 60 °C in an oven to constant mass. The reaction setup and the product are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Reaction setup (left) and product (right)

The samples from the mixer and the reactor were then pressed on the Baopin BR-8170-B hydraulic press into film-like flat round samples or on the Collin P 200 PV hydraulic vacuum press into 2 mm thick round samples for rheometric analyses, both of which are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Hydraulic pressing of the sample

Table 1 lists the samples prepared by mixing and dissolving.

Table 1: PP-MAH based CANs prepared via mixing and dissolving

Sample	Matrix	Additives	Preparation
1	PP-MAH (PO1020)	-	180 °C/60 rpm/30 min
2	PP-MAH (PO1020)	-	170 °C/60 rpm/30 min
3	PP-MAH (PO1020)	-	170 °C/60 rpm/20 min
4	PP-MAH (PO1020)	-	160 °C/60 rpm/20 min
5	PP-MAH (PO1020)	-	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
6	PP-MAH (PO1020)	DGEBA	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
7	PP-MAH (PO1020)	ZnAc	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
8	PP-MAH (PO1020)	ZnAc+DGEBA1	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
9	PP-MAH (PO1020)	ZnAc+DGEBA2	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
10	PP-MAH (PO1020)	ZnAc+DGEBA3	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
11	PP-MAH (PO1020)	ZnAc+DGEBA4	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
12	PP-MAH (PO1020)	ZnAc+DGEBA5	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
13	PP-MAH (PO1020)	DDO	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
14	PP-MAH (PO1020)	ZnAc+DDO1	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
15	PP-MAH (PO1020)	ZnAc+DDO2	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
16	PP-MAH (PO1020)	ZnAc+DDO3	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
17	PP-MAH (PO1020)	ZnAc+DDO4	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
18	PP-MAH (PO1020)	ZnAc+DDO5	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
19	PP-MAH (PO1020)	BDO	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
20	PP-MAH (PO1020)	ZnAc+BDO1	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
21	PP-MAH (PO1020)	ZnAc+BDO2	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
22	PP-MAH (PO1020)	ZnAc+BDO3	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
23	PP-MAH (PO1020)	ZnAc+BDO4	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
24	PP-MAH (PO1020)	ZnAc+BDO5	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
25	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TBD	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
26	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TBD+DGEBA1	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
27	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TBD+DGEBA2	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
28	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TBD+DGEBA3	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
29	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TBD+DGEBA4	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
30	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TBD+DGEBA5	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
31	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TBD+DDO1	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
32	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TBD+DDO2	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
33	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TBD+DDO3	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
34	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TBD+DDO4	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
35	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TBD+DDO5	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
36	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TBD+BDO1	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
37	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TBD+BDO2	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
38	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TBD+BDO3	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
39	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TBD+BDO4	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
40	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TBD+BDO5	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
41	PP-MAH (PO1020)	2,2DTA1	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
42	PP-MAH (PO1020)	2,2DTA2	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
43	PP-MAH (PO1020)	2,2DTA3	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min

44	PP-MAH (PO1020)	4,4DTA1	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
45	PP-MAH (PO1020)	4,4DTA2	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
46	PP-MAH (PO1020)	4,4DTA3	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
47	PP-MAH (PO1020)	BDO	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
48	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TPP	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
49	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TPP+DGEBA1	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
50	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TPP+DGEBA2	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
51	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TPP+DGEBA3	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
52	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TPP+DGEBA4	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
53	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TPP+DGEBA5	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
54	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TPP+DDO1	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
55	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TPP+DDO2	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
56	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TPP+DDO3	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
57	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TPP+DDO4	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
58	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TPP+DDO5	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
59	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TPP+BDO1	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
60	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TPP+BDO2	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
61	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TPP+BDO3	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
62	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TPP+BDO4	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
63	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TPP+BDO5	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
64	PP-MAH (PO1020)	PETMP	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
65	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TBD+PETMP1	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
66	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TBD+PETMP2	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
67	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TBD+PETMP3	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
68	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TBD+PETMP4	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
69	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TBD+PETMP5	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
70	PP-MAH (PO1020)	diPETMP	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
71	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TBD+diPETMP1	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
72	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TBD+diPETMP2	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
73	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TBD+diPETMP3	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
74	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TBD+diPETMP4	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
75	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TBD+diPETMP5	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
76	PP-MAH (PO1020)	ZnAc+PETMP1	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
77	PP-MAH (PO1020)	ZnAc+PETMP2	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
78	PP-MAH (PO1020)	ZnAc+PETMP3	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
79	PP-MAH (PO1020)	ZnAc+PETMP4	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
80	PP-MAH (PO1020)	ZnAc+PETMP5	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
81	PP-MAH (PO1020)	ZnAc+diPETMP1	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
82	PP-MAH (PO1020)	ZnAc+diPETMP2	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
83	PP-MAH (PO1020)	ZnAc+diPETMP3	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
84	PP-MAH (PO1020)	ZnAc+diPETMP4	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
85	PP-MAH (PO1020)	ZnAc+diPETMP5	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
86	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TPP+PETMP1	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
87	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TPP+PETMP2	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
88	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TPP+PETMP3	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min

89	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TPP+PETMP4	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
90	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TPP+PETMP5	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
91	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TPP+diPETMP1	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
92	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TPP+diPETMP2	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
93	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TPP+diPETMP3	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
94	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TPP+diPETMP4	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
95	PP-MAH (PO1020)	TPP+diPETMP5	165 °C/60 rpm/20 min
PP DA ref	PP-MAH (PO1020) - dissolved	-	
PP-g-furan	PP-MAH (PO1020) - dissolved	FFA	130 °C in xylene 1h
DA1	PP-MAH (PO1020) - dissolved	DA 1:0.5 (BMI)	130 °C in xylene 1h
DA2	PP-MAH (PO1020) - dissolved	DA 1:1 (BMI)	130 °C in xylene 1h
DA3	PP-MAH (PO1020) - dissolved	DA 1:2 (BMI)	130 °C in xylene 1h

The synthesis of the materials was followed by characterization. The characterization included insights into the chemical structure using Attenuated total reflectance-Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (ATR-FTIR) and nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR), thermal properties using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), mechanical properties using dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) and rheometric tests.

ATR-FTIR spectra were recorded using a Perkin Elmer Spectrum 65 FTIR spectrometer with a spectral resolution of 4 cm^{-1} and a measurement range of 600 cm^{-1} to 4000 cm^{-1} . Each spectrum was an average of 10 scans. DSC was performed for ABS-based materials in the temperature range from 0 °C to 200 °C and for PP-based materials in the range from -50 °C to 200 °C . All measurements consisted of 2 cycles of heating and cooling with a heating rate of 10 °C/min and in a nitrogen atmosphere with a gas flow of 20 mL/min . The calorimeter was a Mettler Toledo DSC 2.

The TGA was performed using a Mettler Toledo TGA/DSC 3+ thermogravimetric analyser. The method consisted of a 5-minute isothermal segment at 25 °C , followed by heating from 25 °C to 600 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C/min in a nitrogen atmosphere with a gas flow of 20 ml/min . At 600 °C , the atmosphere was switched to oxygen at a flow rate of 20 ml/min and heating continued up to 900 °C .

The DMA experiments were performed on the Perkin Elmer DMA 8000 dynamic mechanical analyser with a heating rate of 2 °C/min , a frequency of 1 Hz and an amplitude of 0.01 mm (temperature scan). They were measured in tensile mode. In addition to the temperature scans, a stress relaxation method was also developed, but this was less successful.

The gel content to determine the degree of cross-linking by dissolving samples in hot xylene for 24 hours was also used.

Following the initial results, upscaling of the most promising materials to the process of reactive compounding was carried out and extended to other polymer matrices, such as maleic anhydride grafted acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS-MAH). The materials produced by reactive extrusion are listed in Table 2. These and the reference materials (PP, PP-MAH, ABS and ABS-MAH) were then injection moulded.

Table 2: Materials prepared via reactive extrusion

Sample	Composition
PP-V1	BDO + TPP; 1:0.5 BDO equiv MAH, 1:0.1 TPP equiv BDO
ABS-V1	BDO + TPP; 1:0.5 BDO equiv MAH, 1:0.1 TPP equiv BDO
PP-V2	DGEBA + TBD; 1:0.5 DGEBA equiv MAH, 1:0.1 TBD equiv DGEBA
ABS-V2	DGEBA + TBD; 1:0.5 DGEBA equiv MAH, 1:0.1 TBD equiv DGEBA
PP-V3	DGEBA + TPP; 1:0.5 DGEBA equiv MAH, 1:0.1 TPP equiv DGEBA
ABS-V3	DGEBA + TPP; 1:0.5 DGEBA equiv MAH, 1:0.1 TPP equiv DGEBA

Due to the high degree of crosslinking of ABS-V3 (indicated by dissolving in acetone), we decided to test the influence of different ratios of the components to enable the flowability of the material to enable 3D printability and general processability of ABS-based CANs. Based on the design of experiments some additional compounds were prepared by reactive compounding and prepared samples are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Design of experiments for ABS-V3

Sample	Composition
822_2024_0036_01	(DGEBA/MA) = 0.25; 5 mol % of catalyst to MA
822_2024_0036_02	(DGEBA/MA) = 1; 5 mol % of catalyst to MA
822_2024_0036_03	(DGEBA/MA) = 0.5; 10 mol % of catalyst to MA
822_2024_0036_04	(DGEBA/MA) = 0.5; 15 mol % of catalyst to MA
822_2024_0036_05	(DGEBA/MA) = 0.125; 5 mol % of catalyst to MA
822_2024_0036_06	(DGEBA/MA) = 0.0625; 5 mol % of catalyst to MA

Due to the promising properties of the PP-V3 material, it was chosen as a matrix for the production of composite materials. Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) and graphite were chosen as fillers, as they have conductive properties and allow spatially selective heating, which could help to trigger (de)bonding. The composites produced are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Composite formulations

Sample	Composition
PP-V3-C0,1	PP-V3 - 0.1 % CNT
PP-V3-C0,55	PP-V3 - 0.55 % CNT
PP-V3-C1	PP-V3 – 1 % CNT
PP-V3-G	PP-V3 – 1 % graphite

Reactive extrusion was carried out using the LabTech LTE 20-44 twin-screw extruder (Figure 5). Reactive extrusion was performed at 50 rpm-1 to reduce throughput and give the components more time to react. The temperature profile was set to drop from 230 °C at the die to 205 °C at the hopper.

Figure 5: Twin screw extruder

Injection moulding of the commercially available reference materials and the prepared upscaled compounds was carried out on the Krauss Maffei CX 50-180 injection moulding machine with the processing parameters listed in Table 5. The injection moulding process was used to produce test specimens in sizes according to the ISO 178, ISO 179, and ISO 527 (type 1BA) standards.

Table 5: Injection molding parameters

Processing parameter	Value
Temperature profile (nozzle to hopper) (°C)	230, 235, 230, 225, 220
Mold temperature (°C)	40
Metering stroke (mm)	20
Decompression (mm)	1
Screw angular velocity (min ⁻¹)	60
Backpressure (MPa)	2.0
Injection velocity (mm/s)	50; 20 - last 1 mm
Switch-over point (mm)	8
Packing pressure (MPa)	80 % of injection pressure
Packing time (s)	10
Rest cooling time (s)	25

The injection moulded specimens were then tested, including insights into chemical structure using ATR-FTIR and MFI, thermal properties using DSC and TGA, mechanical properties using DMA and tensile testing.

ATR-FTIR spectra were recorded using a Perkin Elmer Spectrum 65 FTIR spectrometer with a spectral resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ and a measurement range from 600 cm⁻¹ to 4000 cm⁻¹. Each spectrum was an average of 10 scans.

The melt flow index (MFI) was measured with the LIYI MFI LY-RP device at 230 °C and 2.16 kg for PP samples and 5 kg for ABS-based samples. The test procedure complied with the ISO 1133 standard.

DSC for ABS-based materials was performed in the temperature range from 0 °C to 200 °C and for PP-based materials in the range from -50 °C to 200 °C. All measurements consisted of 2 heating and cooling cycles with a heating rate of 10 °C/min and in a nitrogen atmosphere with a gas flow of 20 ml/min. The calorimeter was a Mettler Toledo DSC 2.

The TGA was performed using a Mettler Toledo TGA/DSC 3+ thermogravimetric analyser. The method consisted of a 5-minute isothermal segment at 25 °C, followed by heating from 25 °C to 600 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C/min in a nitrogen atmosphere with a gas flow of 20 ml/min. At 600 °C, the atmosphere was switched to oxygen at a flow rate of 20 ml/min and heating continued up to 900 °C.

The DMA experiments were carried out using the Perkin Elmer dynamic mechanical analyser, DMA 8000, with a heating rate of 2 °C/min, a frequency of 1 Hz and an amplitude of 0.01 mm. PP-based samples were measured in tensile mode due to their flexibility, ABS-based samples in dual cantilever clamping mode due to their stiffness.

The tensile tests were performed by the ISO 527-1 standard on the Shimadzu AG - X Plus universal testing machine, equipped with a 10 kN load cell. The shape of the specimen was 1BA. The weld strength test of welded specimens was also carried out on the same testing machine, with the measurement consisting of a preliminary test at 1 mm/min up to 3 N of load, followed by 50 mm/min until the break.

The gel content for identification of crosslinking degree via dissolving in acetone for 24 hours was determined for ABS-based samples injection moulded specimen.

All the equipment used is presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Equipment overview

Nr.	Equipment	Method	Location/Partner
1	Kneader Brabender Plasti-Corder Lab-Station EC (Mixer 50 EHT)	165 °C and 60 rpm-1 for 20 min	PCCL
2	Baopin BR-8170-B hydraulic press	170 °C, 1 min + cooling to 25°C at 1.2 MPa	FTPO
3	Collin P 200 PV vacuum hydraulic press	170 °C, (80 bar 3 min, 130 bar 20 min)	PCCL
3	Perkin Elmer Spectrum 65 FTIR	Resolution of 4 cm ⁻¹ and a measuring range from 600 cm ⁻¹ to 4000 cm ⁻¹ , average of 10 scans	FTPO
4	Bruker Avance Neo 400 mHz NMR	Solid state C13	National Institute of Chemistry
5	Mettler Toledo DSC 2	0 °C to 200 °C for ABS and -50 °C to 200 °C for PP; 2 cycles of heating and cooling with a heating rate of 10 °C/min and in a nitrogen atmosphere with a gas flow of 20 mL/min	FTPO
6	Thermogravimetric analyzer Mettler Toledo TGA/DSC 3+	5 min isothermal segment at 25 °C, followed by heating from 25 °C up to 600 °C with a heating rate of 10 °C/min in a nitrogen atmosphere with a gas flow of 20 mL/min. At 600 °C atmosphere was switched to oxygen with a flow of 20 mL/min and the heating continued up to 900 °C.	FTPO
7	Dynamic mechanical analyzer (DMA) Perkin Elmer DMA 8000	heating rate of 2 °C/min, frequency of 1 Hz, and amplitude of 0.01 mm	FTPO
9	Universal testing machine Shimadzu AG - X Plus	ISO 527-1 (1BA specimen)	FTPO
9	LabTech LTE 20-44 twin screw extruder	50 rpm ⁻¹ ; 230 °C at the nozzle to 205 °C at the hopper	FTPO
10	Injection moulding machine Krauss Maffei CX 50-180	See Table 5	FTPO
11	Melt flow index (MFI) LIYI MFI LY-RP	230 °C and 2.16 kg weight for PP samples and 5 kg for ABS based samples	FTPO

Experimental results

Reactive mixing

The first samples were prepared by reactive mixing. Initially, a number of tests were carried out to determine the proper temperature and mixing time for PO 1020. 165 °C and 20 minutes at 60 rpm. proving to be optimal parameters to ensure the best homogenization with the least degradation. The moment and temperature as a function of time for optimal parameters of mixing of PO 1020 are shown in Figure 6. The stabilisation of the moment curve indicates a homogeneous mixture.

Figure 6: Moment (blue) and temperature (red) versus time for mixing of PP-MAH with optimal parameters

In many prepared samples, the success of the crosslinking was already evident in the process itself by an increase of the moment, following the initial increase due to the introduction of solid materials to the mixer, as can be seen in Figure 7 between the 3rd and 6th minute of mixing.

Figure 7: Multiple samples increase after an initial spike in the moment (blue curve) was noticed, indicating successful crosslinking

Solid-state C13 NMR tests were performed to quantify the number of grafted maleic anhydride groups, but solid-state NMR was not sensitive enough to record peaks at 3.1 ppm, and dissolving in various solvents resulted in too viscous solutions, even at elevated temperatures, to perform H NMR testing. The solid-state spectra of PO 1020 are shown in Figure 8.

PP-g-MA-Exxelor.1.fid
 PP-g-MA-Exxelor
 13C CP-MAS
 NIKA (400 MHz NMR spectrometer)
 SPIN @ 10 kHz
 temp = 25 C
 22.02.2024

Figure 8: NMR spectra of PO 1020

ATR-FTIR analysis was the first characterisation technique applied to the composite samples. The results are presented below, but only one representative is shown for each combination for better transparency of the results. Figure 9 shows ATR-FTIR spectra of reference mixed PO 1020 with reference spectra of mixtures with the crosslinkers only added. With each sample containing the crosslinker changes in chemical structure are recorded, however, they can be attributed to differences in crosslinker structure.

Figure 9: FT-IR spectra of reference mixed PO1020 (005) and references with crosslinkers in PO1020 only (006 – DGEBA, 013 – DDO, 019 – BDO, 064 – PETMP and 070 – diPETMP)

When catalysts were introduced into the matrix, no significant differences were detected with ATR-FTIR (Figure 10), as the proportion of catalyst added is presumably too low.

Figure 10: ATR-FTIR spectra of reference mixed PO1020 (005) and reference samples with catalysts only (007 – ZnAc, 025 – TBD, and 048 – TPP)

In Figure 11 reference sample (005) is compared to representatives of each crosslinker in combination with ZnAc catalyst. Sample 092 is quite similar to reference 070 presented in Figure 9. However, with DGEBA and PETMP with the addition of catalyst spectra peaks shift towards the neat reference (005), which could indicate that the crosslinking occurred in the presence of a catalyst.

Figure 11: ATR-FTIR spectra of reference mixed PO1020 (005) and samples with ZnAc as catalyst and various crosslinkers (009 – DGEBA, 015 – DDO, 021 – BDO, 077 – PETMP and 082 – diPETMP)

In Figure 12 reference samples are compared to representative spectra of each combination of crosslinker with TBD catalyst. Visually the mixtures with TBD came out of the mixer more or less brown, indicating degradation. However, a peak at 1740 cm^{-1} , which indicates oxidative degradation does not indicate higher degrees of degradation compared to similar samples with different catalysts, so presumably, coloring is caused by the catalyst chemistry. The spectra of DGEBA is standing out, compared to spectra with DGEBA in previous figures (006 and 009), indicating that TBD and DGEBA are likely to be less promising pairing than ZnAc and DGEBA.

Figure 12: ATR-FTIR spectra of reference mixed PO1020 (005) and samples with TBD as catalyst and various crosslinkers (027 – DGEBA, 032 – DDO, 037 – BDO, 066 – PETMP and 072 – diPETMP)

In Figure 13, the representative combinations of crosslinkers with TPP catalyst are presented. Comparing the spectra to previous references and combinations with other catalysts, there is an indication that the use of TPP generally induces the most changes, and the used catalysts would probably be the best pairing for PETMP and diPETMP.

Figure 13: ATR-FTIR spectra of reference mixed PO1020 (005) and samples with TPP as catalyst and various crosslinkers (050 – DGEBA, 055 – DDO, 060 – BDO, 087 – PETMP and 092 – diPETMP)

From the spectra presented in Figure 14, it can be seen that even if the crosslinkers differ only in the position of the functional group, the differences can be significant. The degradation of specimen 045 is confirmed using other techniques as well since lower gel content, and significant color change was recorded compared to 042.

Figure 14: ATR-FTIR spectra of reference mixed PO1020 (005) and representative samples of systems without catalyst (042 – with 2,2-DTA and 045 – with 4,4-DTA)

Figure 15 shows an example of the characterisation of DSC measurements. Table 7 shows the results of reference samples and representatives for each crosslinker and catalyst combination. The melting of PP-MAH following slow cooling consists of two peaks, however, the resulting enthalpies are more or less in a similar range, regardless of the melting in one or two stages represented by corresponding peaks. Changes in melting and crystallisation behaviour were mainly observed with the addition of all crosslinkers and also some catalysts, with the change being most pronounced with the addition of DGEBA, as can be seen in Figure 16, which shows DSC thermograms of sample 009. The initial two peaks collided into one, suggesting that it may be the crosslinking that is hindering the recrystallisation behaviour.

Figure 15: Reference DSC curves as an example of evaluation

Figure 16: DSC thermographs of sample 009

Table 7: DSC results of reference samples and representative sample for each combination

Sample	T _{onset} (°C) - melting	T _g (°C)	T _{m1} (°C)	T _{m2} (°C)	ΔH _m (J/g)	T _{onset} (°C) - cooling	T _c (°C)	ΔH _{mc} (J/g)
000	150.1	-10.0	156.1	164.1	74.3	116.0	112.3	72.8
005	141.7	-10.0	155.6	162.9	77.5	117.2	113.9	76.2
048	149.7	-9.9	155.6	162.0	78.9	116.6	113.2	76.1
007	153.1	-9.6	159.5		71.2	123.8	120.3	69.1
025	149.7	-10.0	156.2		68.3	118.4	114.6	66.3
006	144.5	-9.9	161.5		76.8	131.3	126.3	74.8
013	150.1	-10.0	157.1		77.8	118.4	114.4	73.4
019	148.9	-10.2	156.3		69.0	119.0	115.4	68.7
064	149.7	-10.1	157.5		73.0	119.2	115.3	71.4
070	151.9	-9.7	157.6		73.8	121.7	118.3	71.2
042	155.6	-10.1	157.2	162.2	80.9	116.4	113.2	78.6
045	149.4	-10.2	162.8		76.3	117.1	112.3	75.2
009	144.6	-10.1	160.2		76.2	131.9	128.0	74.4
015	145.9	-9.9	155.5		70.7	116.7	113.2	70.6
021	148.8	-10.0	156.1		76.3	118.2	114.4	73.7
077	150.8	-9.8	157.8		77.5	119.6	115.9	73.3
082	152.2	-10.1	158.8		74.5	121.3	117.8	72.9
027	137.7	-9.9	160.9		67.9	128.8	122.6	66.2
032	146.6	-10.0	155.5		70.6	117.6	113.6	70.3
037	146.6	-10.3	155.2		74.0	118.1	114.3	72.6
066	147.9	-10.0	155.5		80.7	119.4	115.6	79.8
072	149.5	-10.0	157.5		84.4	120.2	117.0	81.0
050	141.1	-10.1	159.1		74.7	130.0	126.4	73.0
055	144.2	-10.0	154.1		76.5	117.2	113.3	75.0
060	145.1	-10.1	155.3		74.7	118.3	114.5	73.8
087	147.1	-10.1	155.8		76.7	120.6	117.1	74.9
092	148.0	-10.3	156.2		79.2	121.0	117.6	76.6

An example of the evaluation of TGA measurements is shown in Figure 17. The results of reference and representative samples are shown graphically in Figure 18. No significant changes were observed, except for sample 045, which showed an optical deterioration that was also measured using other techniques.

Figure 17: Reference TGA curves as an example of evaluation

Figure 18: Temperatures of degradation and onset temperatures of degradation of reference and representative samples

Figure 19 shows a representative diagram of the dynamic modulus as a function of temperature. The dynamic moduli at 30 °C and 130 °C are shown in Figure 20. An increase in moduli at higher temperatures indicates an increase in stiffness at higher temperatures, which could be due to crosslinking. The highest moduli at elevated temperatures were measured for samples crosslinked with DGEBA. However, samples containing PETMP without catalysts performed the worst, indicating the incompatibility of PP-MAH and PETMP and the need to use catalysts in such systems.

Figure 19: Representative dynamic modulus versus temperature curve

Figure 20: Dynamic Modulus at 30 °C and 130 °C

The determination of the gel content provided interesting additional information. Some results (shown in Figure 21) were surprising, others supported the rest of the results. It was interesting to

note that only the addition of catalysts led to a certain degree of crosslinking. The highest gel content, a bit above 50 %, was found for sample 009 with ZnAc and DGEBA.

Figure 21: Gel content determination results for PP-MAH based mixtures

Dissociative CAN trials

Due to the toxicity of the components, in particular bismaleimide (BMI), which is required for the induction of the Diels-Alder crosslinking mechanism, the tests were carried out exclusively in small-scale chemical laboratory reactors. The resulting precipitated powders were characterized by NMR and ATR-FTIR, but only solid-state NMR spectra could be obtained (Figure 22) as the solutions were too viscous in various solvents, including deuterated xylene and mixtures of deuterated chloroform and benzene. The ATR-FTIR spectra are presented in Figure 23, where the sample with the ratio of BMI to grafted groups of PP-MAH (DA_1-2) contains new peaks that were not recorded in the others, suggesting that the new peaks are likely not solely due to additive content but also due to crosslinking.

PP-DA.1.fid
 PP-DD
 13C CP-MAS
 NIKA (400 MHz NMR spectrometer)
 SPIN @ 10 kHz
 temp = 25 C
 28.02.2024

Figure 22: Reference solid-state NMR spectra of PP-MAH powder crosslinked with BMI in ratio 1:2 (BMI:MA groups)

Figure 23: ATR-FTIR spectra of reference, intermediates, and materials with Diels-Alder mechanism

Upscaling

As already mentioned, the upscaling was performed on a twin-screw laboratory extruder, whereby 3 main tasks were fulfilled. Firstly, 3 of the most promising combinations of crosslinkers and catalysts were tested with PP-MAH and ABS-MAH matrices. Secondly, ABS-V3 was further investigated to determine the best ratio of components to output the best possible material for further tasks. The final part consisted of the production of PP-V3 based composites containing carbon nanotubes (CNT) and graphite (G). The matrix was selected due to its suitability for 3D printing applications.

1. Solid-state NMRs were recorded for ABS-MAH (Figure 24) and PP-MAH (Figure 25). Compared to previously used PP-MAH, the PP-MAH used for upscaling appears to contain more additives, making it more suitable for processing.

ABS-g-MA-Graftabond.1.fid
 ABS-g-MA-Graftabond
 13C CP-MAS
 NIKA (400 MHz NMR spectrometer)
 SPIN @ 10 kHz
 temp = 25 C
 21.02.2024

Figure 24: NMR spectra of ABS-MAH (Graftabond ABS-MAH 00320)

PP-g-MA-Graftabond.1.fid
 PP-g-MA-Graftabond
 13C CP-MAS
 NIKA (400 MHz NMR spectrometer)
 SPIN @ 10 kHz
 temp = 25 C
 20.02.2024

Figure 25: NMR spectra of PP-MAH (Graftabond APP-MAH 00530 C)

Figures 26 and 27 show the ATR-FTIR spectra of PP-based (Fig. 26) and ABS-based samples (Fig. 27). The spectra of PP-V2 and PP-V3 indicate a decrease in the peaks characteristic of maleic anhydride groups (two peaks between 2000 cm^{-1} and 1750 cm^{-1}), indicating a reaction with crosslinkers and possible crosslinking. A similar trend can be seen for ABS-based vitrimers in Figure 27.

Figure 26: ATR-FTIR spectra of PP based specimens as follows PP (822_2024_0005_01_PP), PP-MAH (822_2024_0005_02_PP-g-MA), PP-V1 (822_2024_0005_03_PP V), PP-V2 (822_2024_0005_10_PP V2) and PP-V3 (822_2024_0005_11_PP V3)

Figure 27: ATR-FTIR spectra of ABS based specimens as follows ABS (822_2024_0005_04_ABS), ABS-MAH (822_2024_0005_05_ABS-g-MA), ABS-V1 (822_2024_0005_06_ABS V), ABS-V2 (822_2024_0005_08_ABS V2) and ABS-V3 (822_2024_0005_ABS V3)

A very important first indication of crosslinking was also the decreasing melt flow index, as the crosslinking of materials decreases the flowability of the material. The flowability of the grafted

matrix is higher than that of the pure materials due to additives that are added during the grafting process and are inherent to the manufacturer's know-how. The addition of BDO and TPP impairs the flowability of both ABS-V1 and PP-V1 to a certain extent (see Figure 28).

Figure 28: Melt flow index of initially upscaled mixtures

The following experiments led to an even further decrease in the MFI (Figure 29). The most significant decrease was observed in ABS-V3, where the MFI of the material could not be measured as it was close to zero. This was the main indicator that although the mixture is significantly crosslinked, the resulting material would not flow enough to be processable, thus further adjustment of component ratios was needed to produce material suitable for processing and 3D printing applications.

Figure 29: MFI of second batch of upscaled mixtures

Dissolving ABD in acetone (Figure 30) only gave us approximate observational information about the degree of cross-linking, as the use of metal meshes was out of the question because the mesh was not dense enough (Figure 31), filter paper (Figure 32) gave contradictory results as some materials may be more attracted to the surface of the paper than others due to their chemical structure and polarity, so the test was only used for guidance purposes.

Figure 30: Gel content of ABS-V1

Figure 31: ABS-V3 in metallic net in acetone

Figure 32: Filtering of ABS based samples dissolved in acetone by filter paper

The gel contents of the ABS-based samples vitrimers are presented in Figure 33. ABS-MAH was completely dissolved and should have a gel content of about 10 % due to the attractive forces of the MA groups on the filter paper; when the MA groups are crosslinked, the attractive forces should consequently decrease, so that the results are not comparable. Figure 34 shows parallels of dissolved injection moulded ABS-V3 samples, which have a high gel content and degree of cross-linking.

Figure 33: Gel content of ABS based vitrimers determined via filtration

Figure 34: Dissolved injection molded ABS-V3 specimen in two parallels

Figure 35 presents the representative stress-strain curves that were determined in the tensile test on injection moulded test specimens. In the case of PP-based test specimens, PP stands out because grafting and the corresponding addition of additives significantly changes the material properties. While comparing vitrimers to PP-MAH, PP-V1 changed the least, while PP-V2 strain decreased and strength increased, similarly the strength of PP-V3 increased, while its elongation increased as well. ABS-MAH is also significantly more flexible compared to ABS. In all crosslinking systems, the

toughness increased significantly and the elongation decreased, which indicates a significant crosslinking of the network.

Figure 35: Stress-strain curves of PP (left) and ABS (right) based vitrimers

In Figure 36 the trials for determination of optimal welding/bonding parameters are presented. Various temperatures and times were employed, to yield as little melting indication as possible while obtaining the highest possible welding strength. Figure 37 presents the welding force testing setup.

Figure 36: Determination of optimal bonding parameters

Figure 37: Adhesion testing before (left) and after (right)

Initial welding tests revealed that the highest force needed to break the weld was achieved with samples welded at 160 °C for 2 h as can be seen in Figure 38.

Figure 38: Adhesion testing - parameter determination results

The second step was to weld PP with ABS, PP-MAH with ABS-MAH and PP-V3 with ABS-V3. PP and ABS are incompatible and no adhesive forces occurred between them. Figure 39 presents force-strain curves recorded during this step of the welding test. ABS-V3 shrinks more during welding

compared to ABS-MAH, resulting in a significant reduction in the weld surface area, which must be taken into account when considering the results. With the introduction of MA groups into the materials, welding was already successful due to the attractive bonds between the MA groups and the change in polarity of the matrices. With the introduction of adaptable networks, the weld strength (force measurements) does not increase significantly compared to welding MA grafted matrices as the forces are in the range of standard deviation. However, the best performing sample contained CANs and the weld surface shrank (ABS-V3 only, due to the high injection moulding pressures because of the high degree of crosslinking and the associated low MFR and consequently high residual stress), indicating that the welding method needs to be further optimised.

Figure 39: Adhesion of PP-MAH welded with ABS-MAH compared to PP-V3 welded with ABS-V3

2. The study of optimization of crosslinker and catalyst for ABS-V3 was performed, to ensure good enough flowability of the material for processing and 3D printing. To increase the melt flow rate and flowability it was needed to decrease the crosslinking degree. In Figure 40 FTIR spectra of the samples are presented. The FTIR spectra shows that more MA groups react at higher crosslinker content, which leads to a decrease in the peak at 1780 cm^{-1} . Otherwise, the spectra of 0036_02, which contains the highest content of DGEBA, and 0036_06, which contains the lowest content of crosslinker, are always at the maxima or minima of the corresponding peaks as expected.

Figure 40: FTIR spectra of ABS-V3 component ratio design of experiment

Table 8 shows the results of the MFI determination for the optimisation of the ABS-V3 compositions. The flowability of the material is only maintained at the lowest degree of crosslinking.

Table 8: Melt flow index results

Sample	MFI (g/10 min)
822_2024_0036_01	0.43
822_2024_0036_02	-
822_2024_0036_03	0.16
822_2024_0036_04	0.22
822_2024_0036_05	0.82
822_2024_0036_06	8.25

Table 9 presents the results of the DSC, which show that a higher concentration of crosslinker leads to a lower glass transition temperature and vice versa.

Table 9: Glass transitions and corresponding specific heats determined using DSC

Sample	T _g (°C)	C _p (J/gK)
822_2024_0036_01	103.5	0.24
822_2024_0036_02	99.2	0.24
822_2024_0036_03	102.0	0.25
822_2024_0036_04	101.0	0.24
822_2024_0036_05	104.1	0.22
822_2024_0036_06	104.4	0.26

Table 10 presents the collected results of the TGA for ABS-V3 DoE. The lowest degradation temperature was measured for the specimen with the highest crosslinker content and the highest for the lowest crosslinker content.

Table 10: Gathered results of thermogravimetric analysis

Sample	T_d (°C)	ΔY_1 (%)	Char (%)	Ash (%)
822_2024_0036_01	416.7	97.2	2.3	0.5
822_2024_0036_02	414.3	96.5	2.8	0.7
822_2024_0036_03	415.7	96.9	2.4	0.7
822_2024_0036_04	416.1	97.0	2.3	0.6
822_2024_0036_05	417.5	97.6	2.0	0.4
822_2024_0036_06	420.0	97.7	1.9	0.5

The DMA analysis indicates that the resulting samples are vitrimers that are crosslinked due to the high dynamic modulus above the glass transition, as can be seen from the dynamic modulus curves in Figure 41. Interestingly, samples 0036_03 and 0036_04 perform better above the glass transition temperature than sample 0036_02, which contains the highest content crosslinker. Specimens with the lowest crosslinker content are associated with poorer performance above the glass transition temperature.

Figure 41: Dynamic modulus (logarithmic) versus temperature plots for ABS-V3 design of experiments

The results of the tensile test showed that samples 0036_05 and 0036_06 had the highest tensile strength, as presented by the representative curves in Figure 42. The highest elongation was also found for specimen 0036_05, indicating that this is an optimal formulation to ensure the flexibility of the material. The lowest elongation was measured for 0036_04, the sample with the highest proportion of catalyst. The sample with the highest proportion of crosslinker (0036_02) showed average strength and elongation.

Figure 42: Stress-strain representative curves for ABS-V3 design of experiments

3. The most suitable formulation for 3D printing was used for the preparation of composite materials with carbon nanotubes and graphite. The FTIR spectra of the composites (Figure 43) show the most significant difference in the peak at 1740 cm^{-1} separating the CNT and G reinforced composites, as the G reinforced composite has the lowest peak at a given wavelength.

Figure 43: FTIR spectra of PP-V3 based composites

The MFI results of the composites are presented in Figure 44. PP-V3 reinforced with 0.1 % and 0.55 % of CNT gives an MFI in the range of the standard deviation. However, the addition of 1 % of CNT

lowers the MFI, which is probably due to the presence of the filler. With 1 % of graphite, the resulting MFI is also in the range of the standard deviation compared to a composite with 1 % CNT.

Figure 44: Melt flow index of composites

Table 11 presents DSC results of the composite materials. Comparing the different concentrations of CNT addition, the crystallinity peak shifts to higher temperatures at higher concentrations, which means that crystallisation starts earlier. With 1 % CNT and G, the values are comparable.

Table 11: DSC results of composites

Sample	T_c (°C)	ΔH_c (J/g)	T_{m1} (°C)	ΔH_m (J/g)
822_2024_0050_01	107.1	13.5	163.0	13.9
822_2024_0050_02	108.7	12.5	162.8	12.6
822_2024_0050_03	112.4	12.0	162.5	12.3
822_2024_0050_04	112.1	11.8	162.3	12.0

The thermogravimetric analysis did not show significantly different results, as the degradation temperatures were in the range between 467.9 °C and 468.2 °C and the residues were between 0.6 % and 1 %. The TGA thermographs of the composites are presented in Figure 45.

Figure 45: TGA thermographs of composites

The tensile tests resulted in the representative curves presented in Figure 46. It can be seen that even the lowest CNT content performs better than the addition of 1 % of G. The most significant increase in stiffness and flexibility was observed with the addition of 1 % CNT.

Figure 46: Representative stress-strain curves of composites

The bonding strength was tested for PP-V3-C1%, which exhibited the best mechanical properties when welded with ABS-V3. The results are presented in Figure 47 and are comparable to PP-V3 bonded with ABS-V3. Specimens according to ISO 527 (type 1BA) were used to determine the adhesive strength.

Figure 47: PP-V3-C1% welded with ABS-V3 bonding force versus strain

The bonding and debonding test was performed with an injection moulded specimen of the size specified in ISO 178. An average of about 60 N of force was needed to debond specimens at room temperature (RT), but the force for specimens heated to 160 °C after initial bonding and cooling was less than 16 N on average. However, it must be noted, that the first specimen measured that did practically need no force to debond was closest to 160 °C, and every following specimen tested had a lower temperature, since they were taken out of the oven at the same time, thus increasing in force from first to third sample.

Figure 48: Bonding and debonding tests of PP-V3C1% welded with ABS-V3

Conclusions

Task 1.2 consisted of extensive research into the possible effects of different routes to the preparation of vitrimers since the field is very young and not a lot of literature is available, especially considering the relations and outcomes of different approaches to the preparation of vitrimers using different crosslinkers and catalysts on the same base polymer material. It was found that dependencies regarding the resulting material could not be monotonously determined since there are catalysts that work better with certain types of crosslinkers (TPP and PETMP for example). Generally, the best-performing crosslinker DGEBA (presumably due to its highest reactivity of tested crosslinkers) works better with other catalysts (with ZnAc for example, which indicates the phenomena of crosslinking the material even in the absence of crosslinker).

Dissociative networks based on Diels-Alder chemistry were also produced in the laboratory reactor in the fume hood, but due to the toxicity of the bismaleimide crosslinker, further upscaling was not pursued because of potential health risks. Non-invasive techniques such as FTIR and NMR were used for characterisation.

In general, the most promising and scientifically interesting materials were upscaled – synthesis via reactive extrusion on a twin-screw extruder. Upscaling of PP-MAH based materials resulted in materials that are interesting for 3D printing applications considering their MFI and the fact that PP generally shrinks too much during the 3D printing process. Crosslinking should significantly reduce shrinkage, which could lead to 3D printable polypropylene. The same mechanisms were also applied to the ABS-MAH base, which was chosen due to the 3D printability of ABS. The resulting vitrimers had a very high degree of crosslinking, and consequently a low melt flow index, close to zero, which makes them not 3D printable. With the indications presented, the ABS-V3 design of the experiment was carried out. However, the results showed that only the material with the lowest levels of crosslinkers flowed well enough to be processed using conventional processing techniques. The produced covalent adaptable networks and their components were evaluated by FTIR, NMR, DSC, TGA, DMA and tensile tests.

The following step was to produce the composites with functional fillers on a PP-V3 basis. CNT and G were employed as reinforcement since they could enable spatial-selective heating that could assist in the triggered debonding of multicomponent parts. The composites were prepared via reactive compounding on a twin-screw extruder/compounder, then injection molded, and characterized with the same techniques as previously synthesized CANs. Composite with 1 % of CNT yielded in best mechanical performance and MFI that is suitable for 3D printing applications and was subjected to further welding trials.

Covalent adaptable networks induced in the polymer act as reversible glue between two incompatible parts since incompatible materials were successfully welded at increased temperature and were debonded without significant forces at the same conditions (elevated temperature – 160 °C). The bonding strength was increased from no attractive forces with neat ABS and PP to maximum recorded at welded PP-V3C1% with ABS-V3 when specimens of size according to ISO 178 were used.

Deviations from the GA

We presume that the present report covers all the aspects of Task 1.2, without deviations from GA.

References

1. Montarnal, D., Capelot, M., Tornilhac, F. & Liebler, L. Silica-Like Malleable Materials from Permanent Organic Networks. 965–969 (2011).
2. Hayashi, M. Implantation of recyclability and healing ability into cross-linked commercial polymers by applying the vitrimer concept. *Polymers (Basel)* **12**, (2020).
3. Alabiso, W. & Schlögl, S. The impact of vitrimers on the industry of the future: Chemistry, properties and sustainable forward-looking applications. *Polymers (Basel)* **12**, (2020).
4. Liu, Y. *et al.* External Stimuli-Induced Welding of Dynamic Cross-Linked Polymer Networks. *Polymers* vol. 16 Preprint at <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym16050621> (2024).
5. Shi, Q., Jin, C., Chen, Z., An, L. & Wang, T. On the Welding of Vitrimers: Chemistry, Mechanics and Applications. *Advanced Functional Materials* vol. 33 Preprint at <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.202300288> (2023).
6. Zheng, J. *et al.* Vitrimers: Current research trends and their emerging applications. *Materials Today* **51**, 586–625 (2021).
7. Denissen, W., Winne, J. M. & Du Prez, F. E. Vitrimers: Permanent organic networks with glass-like fluidity. *Chem Sci* **7**, 30–38 (2016).
8. Hammer, L., Van Zee, N. J. & Nicolaÿ, R. Dually crosslinked polymer networks incorporating dynamic covalent bonds. *Polymers (Basel)* **13**, 1–34 (2021).
9. Kissounko, D. A., Taynton, P. & Kaffer, C. New material: vitrimers promise to impact composites. *Reinforced Plastics* **62**, 162–166 (2018).